

INTEGRATING TECHNOLOGY IN LANGUAGE LEARNING MATERIALS

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Abstract. The way people obtain information, learn, and connect with others across the world has changed dramatically as a result of technological advancements. Technology has eliminated distance constraints, allowing higher education to efficiently teach anybody. In order to improve teaching and learning, technology integration is becoming more common in classrooms. A better pattern for recognizing new teaching models has evolved as a result of the fast expansion of technology integration. As a result, it is critical in both learning and teaching language skills.

Keywords: Language Teaching, Integration, Technology, Strategies

INTRODUCTION

Foreign language instruction based on technology has produced numerous effective learning tools. The use of technology in education makes the target language easy to control. Apprentices have higher opportunities to improve their foreign language abilities if they are boosted by technology; thus, technological learning is a major aspect in motivating students into improved learning [1]. Hubbard has argued that technology is fundamental to the process of globalization and has an effect on education and culture.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Due to the introduction of technology, the technique of language education was significantly altered. Technology offers many advantages as education makes progress more exciting and productive. Using technology encourages students to engage and study according to their interests. It was widely recognized in the current world for teaching English. Technology meets students' visual and aural senses. In the classroom, technology may be useful through enabling communication, producing training products, and improving the self-expression of learners [2]. The key role of technology has to be recognized, concluded Farr & Murray in the discussion about the problems of education, training and training. The experts also pointed out that usage of technology in instruction opens up a new field of facts and gives way for transforming current education approaches. Many researchers from many fields have studied the influence on the education of technology.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Educators are the primary drivers of ICT integration in the classroom. If we don't recognize their role in integrating ICT, the learning process will have inadequate impacts [3]. According to [Torsani \(2016\)](#), technology does not have a substantial impact on student accomplishment unless teachers play an active part in its implementation. Kuru Gönen concluded in a study that instructors in education technologies are seen as a major factor. Technology is changing the role of instructors and the activities of the classroom. Teachers are playing a number of functions, according to. Some of the names used to characterize them are experts, formal agencies, personal models, facilitators and delegators. Teachers who are experts should be highly informed in the topic they are teaching and should be a source of information for their pupils. Professors in the role of authority should be well educated in this field and think that students should conform to the regulations of the professors. They are authoritarian in this area. The function of the model is an example to follow and learn from what teachers in a class say, do or signal, and this may have a substantial influence on the growth of their pupils. Teachers that act as facilitator lead and assist the learning processes of their pupils by leading them to learn new things based on knowledge. Delegation teachers provide children with assignments and urge them to be self-employed.

With the incorporation of technology into their classrooms, the role of teachers is transformed. [Hedayati et al. \(2018\)](#) said that the role of students changes with technology integration from passive to active. Classes shift from teachers to students. Teacher-centred classrooms are traditional and passive roles are performed by students. Students get just information during these sessions, while professors have active organizing duties. Teachers plan courses, set class goals and provide their students with feedback. The responsibilities of instructors and students alter with the move from teacher-centred to learner-centred classrooms. The students are engaged, student participants.

By searching and evaluating the relevant literature of the question that "How Technology Promote Learning?" the following results were obtained from the review of the studies [4]:

1. Technology is a tool for the development of knowledge for showing views, understandings and beliefs of learners and for the production of organized learning bases.
2. Technology is a tool for discovering knowledge to promote learning through information access and the comparison of ideas and views of the world.

3. Technology is a genuine environment to promote learning in order to present and stimulate significant challenges, circumstances and contexts, to uncover beliefs, opinions, arguments and to define a space for student thinking in a controllable problem.

4. Technology is a social way to promote learning, discussing, rationalizing and achieving agreement amongst members of society and promoting discussion among knowledge-based groups.

5. Technology is an intellectual partner that promotes learning by enabling learners to say, say, think about what they have learnt and know about it, enable internal dialogue and the building of meaning, make personal meanings and encourage creative thinking. Technology affects the learning of learners positively. It makes students more involved, and so more information can be maintained. Technology offers useful experiences in learning. It allows students to cooperate more with their peers so that they are able to learn from one another.

In finding the answer to the question “The recent developments in technology integration in language learning” the review of the literature indicated that application of new technological tools like multimedia, audio-video visual aids, flipping the class, search engines like google and Wikipedia have sufficiently increased the efficiency of the language learning and teaching of both learners and teachers. The advanced technology application in language learning also provided better communication, comprehension and speaking skills for the learners. The review of literature also indicated that teachers and learners also play an important role in the successful implementation of technology in language learning.

CONCLUSION

Technology, according to the studies reviewed here, offers a wealth of materials and communication possibilities for both teaching and learning languages. To successfully integrate ICT into language classes, tutors or pupils must take on new duties and utilize contemporary tools appropriately. Of course, one of the definitive aims of language learning and teaching in technology is to encourage learners' motivation and learning interests, which may be a useful way of involving them in the linguistic learning process.

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